

1 **Early transcriptional activity during transformation in humans in vivo indicates organized**
2 **activation of a neurotransmission system in cancer.**

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7 We predict this system to function in concert with prototype neurotransmission machinery (PNTXR, PANX,
8 NPYR) in the generation and detection of neuroactive ligands in the CNS (MENF, PENK, CNTF,
9 neuropeptides like NPWBR, and CNS growth factor like VGF and NGF) that orchestrate excitatory
10 (dopaminergic and glutamatergic), inhibitory (GABAergic), or other (glycine, adenosine, histamine)
11 neurotransmitter signaling to translate neuroactive signaling into a ligand-induced changes in membrane
12 potential (KCN, SCN and CACN channels) associated with neurotransmission. The neurotransmission
13 can be thought to be perceived (through activation of a relatively limited set of molecules that function in
14 the CNS) as a chemical state that describes change in neuronal activity, the equivalent of a emotional
15 response in the CNS in higher organisms.

16 Thus, a primitive reward response that reinforces biologic activity associated with progression or disease
17 progression (lymph node and CNS metastasis) with selection or growth benefit like growth factor signaling
18 by coupling a life cycle or cell cycle function with specific chemical states supports effective completion of
19 the tumor life cycle.
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1 **Results**

2 Genes of the neurotransmission system were activated both early during transformation and later but prior
3 to completion of transformation in advanced pre-cancer.

4 I. Genes activated prior to or during pre-cancer.

5 NPTXR

6 ADM5

7 AGTR2

8 Neurotransmission

9 ADRA1D

10 Olfactory, vomeronasal and taste receptors

11 VN1R2

12 VN1R4

13 Axon guidance factors and cues

14 RSPO4

15 NTN5

16 NRSN

17 Neuropeptide and hormone receptors

18 OPRL1

19 GNHR

MC3R Melanocortin receptor

20 II. Genes activated prior to or during advanced pre-cancer.

1 **Discussion**

2
3 Importantly, if a chemical state or nervous signal type when coupled with the stage-specific growth factor
4 signal is effectively transmitted following completion of a function that promotes disease progression or
5 metastasis, the chemical or “emotional” state coupled with the growth promoting function that itself has
6 selection benefit will have reinforced or trained completion of tumor life cycle.

7
8 This reward response does not require or consider additive feedback following progression associated
9 with endogenous (local) neuroactive signals sensed by the tumor, which can be expected to enhance this
10 neurotransmission trained or coupled selection. Thus, a primitive chemical state produced by the
11 neurotransmission system can be expected based on selection resulting from the coupled growth
12 promoting signal to both be selected resulting in reinforced selection of the coupled growth promoting
13 biologic activity, like a growth factor signals that accompany successful completion of even one cell cycle.

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9 Endocrine functions associated with tumor CNS behaviors that are based on adrenergic HPA type
10 signaling are described and indicate activity resembling a tumor-endogenous vagus system but have not
11 yet been fully dissected and allude to a tumor endogenous neurotransmission system with even higher
12 complexity and selection potential couple to reward. Adrenomedullin, corticotropin releasing hormone and
13 renin based signaling in the tumor together with adrenergic and cholinergic signaling is expected to be
14 associated with one of more physiologic functions of the tumor, like endothelial responsiveness and
15 vasopressin.